

INFLUENCE OF SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT ON THE LEARNING EXPERIENCE OF STUTTERERS IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN OWERRI, IMO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigated the influence of the school environment on the learning experience of stutterers in inclusive education in Owerri, Imo State Nigeria. Using a descriptive research design: the study adopted a simple random sampling technique to select 115 identified students who were stutterers in inclusive education settings in Owerri Imo state (boys 62 and girls 53). A validated questionnaire was used to collect data from participants. Data were analyzed using the Student's t-test and mean statistical tools at a 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that stuttering negatively impacted on the educational learning experience and well-being of students who are stutterers, having obtained a grand or composite mean value of 3.12 which is far higher than the benchmark score of 2.50. Also, there was a significant mean score difference in the learning experience of male and female students who are stutterers as male students are much more affected by the stuttering disorder than female students in inclusive educational settings in Owerri. Therefore, it is recommended that students who are stutterers should endeavor to participate fully in classroom teaching and learning experience and practice their reading repeatedly so as to develop the capacity to master the pronunciations of words, sounds and syllables.

Keywords: Learning experience; Inclusive education; School environment; Stutterers

Introduction

Inclusive education is a fundamental educational philosophy that provides every individual with the opportunity to access quality education on an equitable basis, regardless of any developmental or situational circumstances that may pose barriers to their learning. It aims to allow all learners to develop their intellectual abilities and acquire knowledge without discrimination. Inclusive education fosters an environment where all learners can improve their communication and social skills in a typical learning setting.

However, the typical school environment can be intimidating for many children, as attending school is a significant transition in their developmental experience. For students who stutter, their school experiences can be either supportive or frustrating. Stuttering can temporarily hinder their ability to express themselves fluently, leading to repetition of syllables or words, getting stuck on a word, or visibly struggling to communicate. As a result, students who stutter face unique learning challenges at school, including social difficulties such as teasing or bullying.

Research has shown that more than half of students who stutter are teased or bullied regularly, and they may be perceived as less popular than their classmates. These experiences may lead them to adopt shy and quiet personalities, become anxious, avoid speaking in class, or sit at the back of the classroom to avoid drawing attention to themselves. They may also be particularly sensitive to evaluation by teachers or peers and may refrain from participating in class discussions out of fear of stuttering (Onslow, 2022).

The negative effects of stuttering can have a compounding impact on a student's overall well-being and learning abilities. Stuttering, a speech disorder, can disrupt the coherence of spoken language, affecting the expression of ideas and sounds by causing unpleasant repetition of words, difficulty in articulating sounds, and elongation of words during speech. This experience is often accompanied by anxiety. With over 60 million people affected by stuttering, students who stutter are often subjected to teasing, leading to feelings of frustration, dejection, anger, and aggression. Stuttering is commonly referred to as uncontrolled dysfluency in oral expression, characterized by the repetition of words, sounds, or syllables, as well as prolonged pauses during verbal communication. This can lead to the expression of negative emotions by the affected person, impairing their self-concept, personality, identity, self-esteem, and academic achievement (Learning Loft, 2019).

Khan (2015) observed that the human environment significantly influences the development of stuttering. This is based on the idea that a demanding and stressful environment could lead children to struggle in developing fluent speech. While the school learning environment may not cause stuttering, it can negatively impact a student who already has speech difficulties, making it challenging for them to develop fluency in speech. Stuttering involves strain in speech production and is consistently characterized by stressful repetition of words, syllables, sounds, or phrases, such as "to-to-to-tomorrow." Prolongations refer to the abnormal lengthening of continuant sounds, for example, "mmmmmmilk" for "milk," or sound prolongations like "sssss-salad" and "ffffff-fish." A person who stutters may exhibit various physical reactions, including muscle tension in speech-related muscles (tongue, jaw, lips, or chest) and tension in muscles unrelated to speech (such as shoulders, limbs, and forehead). Alongside these physiological reactions, individuals who stutter often experience negative emotional reactions to the disorder, including embarrassment, guilt, and frustration.

Marder (2020) discovered that students who stutter often experience social discomfort during classroom teaching and learning, as well as during interactions with peers and significant others both inside and outside the classroom. Their inability to pronounce words competently without disruptions presents a compounding challenge for them. For instance, Marder recounted an incident where a student who stuttered emailed her teachers before coming to school, expressing, "It takes a bit for me to say what I want to say," and requesting patience. This illustrates the student's potential nervousness when speaking or reading in front of her classmates, and her proactive approach in seeking the understanding and support of her teacher. The expectation is for teachers to assist these students in effectively participating in the teaching and learning process in a way that brings them joy in communication.

This suggests that the social communication difficulties often experienced by students who stutter could make them vulnerable to teasing or bullying at school, leading them to become unnecessarily quiet, withdrawn, nervous, shy, and anxious, preferring to go unnoticed. They often find it extremely challenging to speak in front of the class. Tasks such as reading aloud, speaking, asking questions, or making presentations among their peers during classroom activities can easily cause them to experience anxiety and stress. As a result, they might pretend not to know the answers to questions asked by their teachers in order to avoid embarrassment. When students who stutter find themselves in situations requiring verbal communication, they may try to keep their sentences as short as possible, avoid using complex words, rely on gestures to express themselves without using words, or allow their peers to finish their sentences for them (Goodwill Report, 2021).

It has been observed that students who stutter often develop low self-confidence, which has negative consequences on their educational attainment in school. Bullying is also a major predicament experienced by students who stutter, as they tend to face unique challenges when interacting with fellow students, peers, and teachers in school. These difficulties lead them to exhibit negative attitudes during classroom learning and social activities, further causing students who stutter to fall behind in learning concepts and skills during their educational experience. Therefore, when stutters avoid speaking or decline to participate in classroom activities, it ultimately affects their grades and their ability to learn important concepts (Busy Bee Speech, 2022).

Statement of the Problem

Students who are stutters tend to evade the communication of difficult words and opportunities to speak in public, instead, they prefer using gestures and short sentences to communicate, to avoid being jested at, bullied or teased. The instance of reading out, making presentations, and answering questions in class could be embarrassing and a source of immense anxiety to stutters in school. For these reasons, students who stutter may not contribute appropriately to classroom teaching and learning experience. The consequences of these dispositions could be poor academic attainment.

Purpose of the Study

This study empirically investigated the influence of the school environment on the learning experience of stutters in inclusive education in Owerri and it specifically determined if:

1. School environment influences the learning experience of students who stutter in an inclusive education setting.
2. Differences exist in the learning experience of male and female students who stutter in an inclusive education setting.

Research Questions

1. Does the school environment influence the learning experience of students who are stutters in an inclusive education setting?
2. Does difference exist in the learning experience of male and female students who are stutters in inclusive education settings?

Methods

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. 115 identified students who are stutters in inclusive education settings in Owerri Imo state (boys 62 and girls 53) were randomly selected for the study.

Influence of School Environment on the Learning Experience of Stutters Scale was used to measure the implication of stuttering on students' learning experience in Owerri Imo state. It is an eight-item self-constructed scale with items such as: I severally repeat words I tend to pronounce and it makes me feel bad; Always I make more than five repetitions of words in a sentence; I always feel frustrated and embarrassed in class when I read, etc. This instrument was validated using the test-retest method after a two-week interval and a reliability coefficient of 0.86 was obtained.

Procedure

The researchers obtained permission from school authorities of the schools used for the study. Also, the researchers sought the consent of the respondents and their teachers. The essence of the study was explained to them and thereafter the questionnaire was administered to them and collected after completion. It took the researchers three weeks to conclude this process.

Data Analysis

Data was analyzed using student t-test and mean analysis statistical tools at 0.05 level of Significance.

Results

Table 1: Demographic and Developmental Characteristics of Respondents

Description	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	62	53.91%
Female	53	46.09%
Total	115	100

Table 1 and Fig shows that out of 115 respondents used for the study, 62 (53.91%) were males, and 53 (46.09%) were females.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Level of Education

Description	Frequency	Percentage
Education		
JSS 3	18	15.65%
SSS 1	33	28.70%
SSS 2	37	32.17%
SSS 3	27	23.48%
Total	115	100

Table 2 and Fig 2 show that among the respondents, 18 (15.65%) are in JSS 3, 33 (28.70%) in SSS 1, 37 (32.17%) in SSS 2, and 27 (23.48%) in SSS3.

Research Question One: Does the school environment influence the learning experience of students who are stutterers in an inclusive education setting?

Table 3: Mean and Rank Order of students who are stutters in an inclusive education setting Response to the Influence of School Environment on the Learning Experience of Stutterers Scale

S/N	My Experience During Learning	Mean	Rank
4	I severally repeat words I tend to pronounce and it makes me feel bad	3.38	1 st
	I feel sad repeating the same sounds while speaking	3.32	2 nd
5	always make more than ten repetitions	3.27	3 rd
6	Always I make more than five repetitions of words in a sentence	3.16	4 th
2	I always feel frustrated and embarrassed in class when I read	3.10	5 th
3	I always avoid reading aloud in the classroom	3.01	6 th
7	Always afraid to ask or answer questions in class	2.86	6 th
8	I am always afraid to speak in the classroom	2.83	8 th
	Composite Mean $\Sigma(x) / \Sigma(N) = 24.93/8$	3.12	

Table 3 shows that all 8 items on the Influence of School Environment on the Learning Experience of Stutterers scale have mean scores that are above the average (benchmark) mean value of 2.50 for determining the high or low extent of the negative influence of stuttering on the learning experience of stutterers in inclusive school settings in Owerri, Imo state. Overall, the experience of stuttering has impacted negatively on the educational well-being of students who are stutterers having gotten a grand or composite mean value of 3.12 which is far higher than the benchmark score of 2.50.

Research Question Two: Does a difference exist in the learning experience of male and female students who are stutterers in inclusive education, setting?

Table 4: t-test analysis on mean score difference in the learning experience of male and female students who are stutters in an inclusive education setting

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Crit-t	Cal-t	DF	P
Male	62	40.92	11.41	1.96	3.21	113	Sig
Female	53	38.71	9.37				

The result in Table 4 reveals that the mean score difference in the learning experience of male and female students who are stutters in inclusive education settings is significant (Crit-t = 1.96, Cal. t = 3.21. df = 113. P < .05 level of significance). The mean and standard deviation revealed that male students are much more affected by stuttering disorder than female students in inclusive educational settings in Owerri.

Discussion of Findings

The research findings indicate that the experience of stuttering has a negative impact on the educational learning experience and overall well-being of students who stutter. The average score obtained was 3.12, significantly higher than the benchmark score of 2.50. This aligns with Khan's (2015) assertion that the environment plays a significant role in the development of stuttering. Stressful and demanding environments can lead to difficulties in developing fluent speech, even though the school environment does not cause stuttering. The strain caused by stuttering is characterized by repetitive and prolonged speech patterns, as well as physical and emotional reactions such as muscle tension, embarrassment, guilt, and frustration.

Marder (2020) discovered that students who stutter experience social discomfort during classroom activities and interactions with peers and others both inside and outside the classroom. Their struggle to speak fluently presents a significant challenge for them. For instance, Marder recounted an incident where a student emailed her teachers before coming to school, expressing the difficulty she faced in speaking and requesting patience and support. This highlights the student's potential nervousness when called upon to speak or participate in class, and her proactive approach to seeking understanding and assistance from her teacher. It is important for teachers to help these students find ways to actively engage in the learning process and communication, fostering an environment where they can experience joy in participation.

The findings from research question two suggest that male students are more significantly affected by stuttering in inclusive educational settings in Owerri compared to female students. This trend may be attributed to the intimidating nature of the typical school environment for most children, as attending school represents a major developmental milestone in their lives. For students who stutter, their school experiences can vary from being

highly supportive to frustrating. Stuttering can temporarily hinder their ability to express themselves eloquently, leading to replication of syllables, getting stuck on words, and visible struggles to communicate effectively. As a result, students who stutter face unique learning challenges and may encounter social difficulties, including teasing or bullying, and being rated as less popular than their classmates. Consequently, they may develop shy and quiet personalities, experience anxiety, avoid speaking in class, or sit at the back to avoid attention. These students may also be particularly sensitive to evaluation by teachers or peers and may refrain from participating in class discussions out of fear of stuttering. The negative impact of stuttering on students' well-being and learning competence can be substantial, as it affects their ability to communicate coherently and can lead to feelings of frustration, dejection, anger, and expressed aggression. Stuttering, characterized by repetition of words, sounds, or syllables, and prolonged pauses during verbal communication, can significantly impair self-concept, personality, identity, self-esteem, and academic achievement.

Conclusion

The findings of this study have helped project the fact that an inclusive school learning, environment could have a negative impact on stutterers' educational learning experience and there is a need for concerned stakeholders to be conscious of it.

Recommendations

- Teachers should carefully pay attention to the learning challenges of students who are stutterers in school, be patient with them and encourage them to develop appropriate coping mechanisms that will help them overcome their educational shortcomings.
- Students who are stutterers should endeavour to participate fully in classroom teaching and learning experience and practice their reading repeatedly so as to develop the capacity to master the pronunciations of words, sounds and syllables.
- Teachers should ensure stutterers are not bullied or jested by their peers so as to avoid them feeling frustrated, dejected and discouraged from trying better in classroom teaching and learning process,

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